

ISic1570

I.Sicily inscription 1570

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

tuff

(yellow)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance

Contrada Buffa, a necrop

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8758

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. οἴμοι ὄ [---]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284894

EDR 112421

EDCS 41300070

PHI 175682

Bibliography

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At

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